

GENRE CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN NEWSPAPER LANGUAGE

Rakhimova Zarina

Asia International University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10896700>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23th March 2024

Accepted: 29th March 2024

Online: 30th March 2024

KEYWORDS

Articles, journals, style and standard, newspapers, publications, and reports.

ABSTRACT

Writing for newspapers began in England in the seventeenth century. By the end of the sixteenth century, brief news booklets started to appear. Any such newspaper would either focus on a single topic or provide news from a single source. Observe the headings of a few of the first news booklets: "News from Spain and Holland" (1593), "News from Stukely's and Morice's Rebellion, a brief rehearsal" (1579), and "Wonderful and strange news out of Suffolke and Essex, where it rained wheat the space of six or seven miles." (1583). Although news pamphlets were clearly the direct ancestors of the British press, they only sometimes appeared and cannot be classified as newspapers.

Introduction. The Daily Courant, the earliest English daily newspaper, was published on March 11, 1702. As mentioned in the publisher's inaugural issue, the publication included mostly international news and no commentary, as the latter went against the publisher's values. As a result, the early English newspaper served primarily as a source of information. Later on, commentary became a frequent element in the publications. But as far back as the middle of the 18th century the British newspaper was very much like what it is today, carrying on its pages news, both foreign and domestic, advertisements, announcements and articles containing comments. However, the British newspaper was much the same as it is today even as early as the middle of the 18th century, publishing commentary-filled articles, announcements, ads, and both domestic and international news on its pages.

The late 17th and early 18th centuries saw the emergence of the American newspaper, which was brought to the country by British settlers. The English newspaper took over a century to develop a unique style and set of standards. Furthermore, newspaper English may only be considered to have evolved as a system of language media and distinct functional style by the 19th century. The following are some ways that modern newspapers and earlier newspapers differ from one another in terms of journalism practices:

Since most stories in early newspapers were only two or three sentences long, your search may turn up a lot of results with little to no useful content. The only articles you find on

your topic can be short ones because the full-length pieces that are typical in contemporary publications are uncommon in older ones. You can anticipate reading a story that combines editorial commentary with factual news. Early newspapers did not follow the current practice of trying to make a clear distinction between opinion, analysis, and factual reporting. Acknowledge the various ways that language has evolved from the 19th century to the current day. Not all terms from the past still have the same meanings today; in many instances, terms have become outmoded or antiquated.

For instance: hornswoogle, transitory, consuming, Yanks. These publications may employ terminology that are today deemed unpleasant and insulting, or they may stereotype specific people or groups. These things reflect the attitudes, beliefs, and viewpoints of the time. Mammy, colored, Huns, and savages are a few examples.

The specific conditions of newspaper publication, the restrictions of time and space, have left an indelible mark on newspaper English. For more than a century writers and linguists have been vigorously attacking "the slipshod construction and the vulgar vocabulary" of newspaper English. The very term *newspaper English* carried a shade of disparagement. Yet, for all the defects of newspaper English, serious though they may be, this form of the English literary language cannot be reduced — as some purists have claimed — merely to careless slovenly writing or to a distorted literary English. This is one of the forms of the. Like every other style, English literature is distinguished by a distinct communicative goal and a unique system of linguistic devices. Newspaper style may not apply to everything that is printed in newspapers. The content seen in today's newspapers is incredibly varied.

On the pages of a newspaper one finds not only news and comment on it, press reports and articles, advertisements and announcements, but also stories and poems, crossword puzzles, chess problems and the like. Since the latter serve the purpose of entertaining the reader, they cannot be considered specimens of newspaper style. It is newspaper printed matter that performs the function of informing the reader and providing he with an evaluation of the information published that can be regarded as belonging to newspaper style.

Hence, a system of connected lexical, phraseological, and grammatical devices that the community views as a distinct language unity and which functions to inform and instruct the reader can be used to characterize English newspaper style. First and foremost, information is communicated in the English newspaper via:

- 1) Quick news items;
- 2) press reports (parliamentary, court procedures, etc.);
- 3) articles that are solely informative;
- 4) announcements and advertisements.

The newspaper also seeks to influence public opinion on political and other matters. Elements of appraisal may be observed in the very selection and way of presentation of news, in the use of specific vocabulary, such as *allege* and *claim*, casting some doubt on the facts reported, and syntactic constructions indicating a lack of assurance on the part of the reporter as to the correctness of the facts reported or his desire to avoid responsibility (for example, 'Mr. X was said to have opposed the proposal'; 'Mr. X was quoted assaying..'). The headlines of news items, apart from giving information about the subject-matter, also carry a considerable

amount of appraisal (the size and arrangement of the headline, the use of emotionally coloured words and elements of emotive syntax), thus indicating the interpretation of the facts in the news item that follows. But, of course, the principal vehicle of interpretation and appraisal the newspaper article, and the editorial in particular. Editorials (leading articles or leaders) are characterized by a subjective handling of facts, political or otherwise. They have much in common with classical specimens of publicistic writing and are often looked upon as such. However, newspaper evaluative writing unmistakably bears the stamp of newspaper style. Thus, it seems natural to regard newspaper articles, editorials included, as coming within the system of English newspaper style. But it should be noted that while editorials and other articles in opinion columns are predominantly evaluative, newspaper feature articles, as a rule, carry a considerable amount of information, and the ratio of the informative and the evaluative varies substantially from article to article.

Conclusion. Finally, I would like to point out that the fundamental element that builds a literary work is the writer's unique, useful style. Newspaper style is a form of mass media communication as well, and it needs to be rich in stylistic elements that provide color and significance to the piece. The English language's newspaper style has a long and rich history, and it continues to evolve through time by incorporating various sources, styles, and stylistic and functional devices.

References:

1. International Congress of Linguistics, The Hague, 1964.
2. Kukhareno V.A. Seminars in Style. Moscow 1971.
3. Leech G.N. English in Advertising. London. Longmans, 1966
4. Арнольд И.В. Стилистика Современного английского языка. Л., 1973.
5. Гальперин И.Р. Очерки по стилистике английского языка. Москва 1958.
6. Гвоздев А.И. Очерки по стилистике английского языка. Москва 1952.
7. Кожина М.Н. К основаниям функциональной стилистики. Пермь 1968.
8. Bafoeva, R. (2024). POSTMODERNISM IN LITERATURE. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 4(3), 86-90.
9. Bafoeva, R. (2023). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK MAQOLLARIDA TA'LIM TUSHUNCHASI.
10. Bafoeva, R. (2023). XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHNING YANGICHA USULLARI.